

Effectiveness of Fast Bowlers Performance Relation with Specific Physical Fitness Variables

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was effectiveness of fast bowlers' performance between specific physical fitness variables. The 150 male fast bowlers were selected Inter- University representation in the academic year of 2015-2016, 2016-2017 and 2018-19 in Andhra Pradesh on non-randomly by purposive sample was used. Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation was used to Analysis of the collected data on specific physical fitness variables were speed (0.585*), dynamic balance, (0.364*), dynamic Flexibility (0.259*), aerobic endurance (0.239*), muscular endurance (0.462*), agility (0.299*), reaction ability (0.379*), accuracy (0.271*) coordination (0.573*) and power (0.565*) coefficient of correlation with fast bowlers' performance had been positively with significant level 0.05. Remaining fitness variables did not correlate on this current study. Key words: Specific Fitness, Variables, Performance, Fast Bowlers etc

Introduction

Cricket is a game played with a bat and a ball. The game can last anywhere from 4 hours to 5 days depending on the format. Played between two teams of eleven players, each team takes it in turn to bat, whilst the opposite team fields the ball. The batting will continue until each batsman is out or a specified number of overs have been bowled. At that point the teams switch roles and the opposing team comes in to bat. The team with the most runs at the end wins. It is a unique sport in that it is a series of individual battles put together to create a team game. Fast bowlers are considered some of the most significant players on the cricket field. Bowling in cricket involves an initial run-up, numerous rotations and circumduction of a straight arm about the glen humeral joint to propel a ball at a batter. Put simply, the bowling action comprises of a short phase of acceleration, followed by a bound, a landing and a launch – think of a javelin throw. However, unlike Javelin this unhealthy, stressful movement is repeated numerous times, over months, days and hours. This complex movement has been researched thoroughly over many years. Current research has shown that at front foot contact, ground reaction forces can be as high as 8 to 12 times bodyweight. Epidemiological research has also shown that young and adolescent fast bowlers are at the highest injury risk, which has led most of the interventional studies to predominately focus on reducing injury incidence in this population. Less attention has actually been focused on the enhancement of bowling performance. There has however been recent increased interest from scientists, researchers and strength and conditioning coaches in the long-term development of the youth population. A major giver to high level fast bowling performance is the velocity at which a bowler can deliver the ball. However, there is limited scientific information on the characteristics which relate to fast bowling ball speed. A number of reviews have concluded that although past investigators have correlated certain biomechanical attributes to high bowling speeds, none confirm any strong relationships between components of the technique and faster bowling speeds. Despite this lack of consensus, run up speed is one important determinant of release speed as well as other correlating attributes such as strength, greater physical stature and overall muscle morphology. This lack of research led criteria means that skills coaches are still inconclusive as to what attributes contribute to creating a fast bowler. Despite, or because of this lack of clarity, Strength and Conditioning coaches are evermore interested on how to develop physical capacities to enhance bowling performance. Essentially fast bowlers are a prize asset in any professional cricket team. With only around six in a squad, keeping them available to train and play is critical to winning games, trophies and championships. This is a tricky business at times and requires an integrated approach involving all the members of the coaching/support team as well as intricate workload management, physical conditioning and player monitoring. The high level of skill required to play Cricket,

a successful player needs good balance and core strength, speed for running between the wickets and in the field, and fast bowlers particularly need very good speed and power. However, which of these are more important? And what are the specific fitness components needful for effective and successive fast bowlers?

Methodology: This study would be decided the effectiveness of fast bowlers' performance association with specific physical fitness variables. Selection of the Subjects: 150 male fast bowlers were selected Inter- University representation in the academic year of 2015-2016, 2016-2017 and 2018-19 in Andhra Pradesh State on non-randomly by purposive sample had been used.

Figure-I: Specific Physical Fitness Variables

S. No	Specific Physical Fitness Variables	Test
1	Coordination	Baseball throw
2	Reaction ability	Nelson Reaction Test
3	Dynamic Balance	Balance Test
4	Static Balance	Balance Test
5	Dynamic Flexibility	Flexibility Test
6	Static Flexibility	Sit and Reach Test
7	Accuracy	Accuracy Test
8	Power	Standing broad jump
9	Maximum Strength	1Rm Test
10	Anaerobic endurance	Margarian Kalamen
11	Aerobic endurance	Vo2max Test
12	Muscular Endurance	Push Ups
13	Endurance	600 Yard Run
14	Agility	Shuttle Run
15	Speed	30 Mts Run

Collection of the Data and Tools

The data had been collected by administrating the standard procedures for taking specific physical fitness variables as well as fast bowlers' performance and tools were used stopwatches, push up stands, spirometer and Flexible measuring tape for flexibility. The score had been recorded time in the nearest one tenth of the seconds and nearest centimeters.

Statistical Analysis and Discussions

In order to find out the relationship of specific physical fitness variables with fast bowlers' performance with the Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation had been used and testing the Hypothesis the level of confidence is 0.05.

Figure-II: Specific Physical Fitness Variables Association with Fast Bowlers Performance

S. No	Specific Physical Fitness Variables	Coefficient of Correlation 'r'
1	Coordination	0.573*
2	Reaction ability	0.379*
3	Dynamic Balance	0.364*
4	Static Balance	0.157
5	Dynamic Flexibility	0.259*
6	Static Flexibility	0.169
7	Accuracy	0.271*
8	Power	0.565*
9	Maximum Strength	0.153
10	Anaerobic endurance	0.197
11	Aerobic endurance	0.239*
12	Muscular Endurance	0.462*
13	Endurance	0.233
14	Agility	0.299*
15	Speed	0.585*

N=150, $r_{.05(150)} = 0.238$, *Significant at 0.05 level.

An analysis of the above table reveals that fast bowlers had been significantly related to specific physical fitness variables were speed (0.585*), dynamic balance, (0.364*), dynamic Flexibility (0.259*), aerobic endurance (0.239*), muscular endurance (0.462*), agility (0.299*), reaction ability (0.379*), accuracy (0.271*) coordination (0.573*) and power (0.565*) as obtained values of correlation were greater than the value of $r = 0.238$ the correlation to be significant at 0.05 specific physical fitness variables were Endurance, Maximum Strength, Static Flexibility, Static Balance and Anaerobic endurance as their correlation values are less than the value of $r = 0.238$ need for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Figure-III Specific Physical Fitness Variables and Fast Bowlers Performance

As for the results finally, the study exposes that fast bowlers' performance would be significantly related to specific physical fitness variables were speed (0.585*), dynamic balance, (0.364*), dynamic Flexibility (0.259*), aerobic endurance (0.239*), muscular endurance (0.462*), agility (0.299*), reaction ability (0.379*), accuracy (0.271*) coordination (0.573*) and power (0.565*). As per the analysis, suggestion to the coaches, physical directors, physical education teachers, physical instructors to concentrate on the above specific physical fitness variables while selecting or screening for fast bowlers in a basic level. It would be given effective and good performance in a specific competition.

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